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Compact Partitioned Average Vector Field Method for Klein-Gordon Schrödinger Equation

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Abstract

Many PDEs can be cast into infinite-dimensional Hamiltonian system. In this paper, the Klein-Gordon Schrödinger (KGS) is considered as a finite dimensional Hamiltonian system. The KGS equation is discretized by a compact scheme and a finite dimensional Hamiltonian system is obtained. Then, we propose and study several accurate numerical methods for solving one-dimensional KGS equation. Discrete conservation laws of the proposed schemes are analyzed. Numerical examples are given to show the accuracy, stability and the efficiency of the new methods.

Key words and Phrases: Compact scheme, Average vector field method, Geometric integration, Finite difference, Klein Gordon Schrödinger equation

1 Introduction

In this study a new conservative compact finite difference method is proposed for the numerical solution of the one-dimensional Klein-Gordon Schrödinger (KGS) equation [1, 2]

$$\begin{aligned} i\psi_t + \frac{1}{2}\psi_{xx} + g\psi\phi &= 0, \quad a < x < b, \quad 0 < t \leq T \\ \phi_{tt} + \phi_{xx} + \mu^2\phi + \psi\bar{\psi} &= 0, \quad a < x < b, \quad 0 < t \leq T \end{aligned} \quad (1.1)$$

with initial conditions

$$\psi(x, 0) = \psi_0(x), \quad \phi(x, 0) = \phi_0(x), \quad \phi_t(x, 0) = \phi_1(x), \quad a \leq x \leq b, \quad (1.2)$$

and periodic boundary conditions

$$\psi(a, t) = \psi(b, t), \quad \phi(a, t) = \phi(b, t), \quad 0 < t \leq T. \quad (1.3)$$

The KGS equation (1.1) represent the classical model of dynamics for interaction of conserved complex nucleon fields ψ with neutral real scalar meson fields ϕ . The constant μ describes mass of a meson and g a coupling real constant.

The Initial Boundary Value (IBV) problem (1.1)-(1.3) is known to possess the following conservation laws:

$$\begin{aligned} M(t) &= \int_a^b |\psi(x, t)|^2 dx = M(0), \\ E(t) &= \frac{1}{2} \int_a^b \left\{ \phi(x, t)^2 + \phi_t^2(x, t) + \phi_x^2(x, t) + |\psi_x(x, t)|^2 - 2\phi(x, t)|\psi(x, t)|^2 \right\} dx \end{aligned} \quad (1.4)$$

which are known as conservation mass and conservation energy (or squared L^2 -norm), respectively. As for mathematical studies are concerned, many studies have been developed for equation (1.1). In the case of one space dimension, the existence of global solutions of the Cauchy problem has been established by the authors [3]. The mathematical properties of the system (1.1) such as attractors [4], global solution [5], asymptotic behavior and stability [6] have been well established in the literature. As for numerical studies of the IBV problem (1.1)-(1.3) many efficient numerical methods have been proposed. Zhang et al. [7] constructed a finite difference method and analyzed the convergence of the method on the basis of the priori estimates and inequalities about norms. Wang et. al. [8] proposed a class of discrete-time orthogonal spline collocation schemes by using piecewise cubic Hermite interpolations in space combined with finite difference methods in time. Xiang [9] constructed the conservative spectral scheme. Boa et. al. [10] presented efficient, unconditionally stable and accurate numerical methods for approximations of the KGS equations with/without damping term. Dehghan et. al. [11] proposed the Chebyshev pseudospectral collocation method for the approximation in the spatial variable and the explicit Runge–Kutta method in time discretization. Kong et. al. [12] propose a quasi norm conservative multisymplectic scheme. Kong. et. al. [13] proposed an explicit mass and energy conserving symplectic partitioned Runge–Kutta Fourier pseudo-spectral scheme. Hong. et. al. [14] proposed an explicit multi-symplectic schemes. Zhang et. al. [15] proposed a conservative finite difference scheme. Zhang [22] proposed Sinc collocation discrete gradient method. Another numerical method used to calculate finite difference approximations is the compact method [16]. They are derived using a Taylor series expansion. Compared to non-compact counterparts of the same order of accuracy, higher-order compact schemes utilize a smaller stencil, have smaller truncating errors, and provide an effective way of combining the robustness of finite difference schemes and the accuracy of spectral methods [17]. However, due to difficulties arising from compact operators, the energy

method cannot be used directly on the compact difference scheme, and therefore the unconditional L^∞ -norm error estimation of any compact difference scheme for nonlinear partial differential equations may not always be straightforward. Wang [18] propose a compact finite difference scheme for computing the KGS equations with homogeneous Dirichlet boundary conditions and introduced a new technique to obtain the optimal convergent rate except for the standard energy method.

It is known that non-conservative scheme may not give reliable results and produces nonlinear blow-up in numerical soliton [24]. To overcome this difficulty structure-preserving algorithms have been concerned by many authors over the last two decades. Recently, the energy-preserving Average Vector Field (AVF) method have been developed systematically in tackling with Hamiltonian ODEs and has been analyzed in the framework of B-series [21]. The AVF method is a discrete gradient method [20]. Some of the features that distinguish the AVF method among discrete gradient methods are its simplicity of implementation, automatic preservation of linear symmetries, and reversibility with respect to linear reversal symmetries [19]. Another prominent feature of the AVF method is that it can preserve the correct monotonic decay of the energy for PDEs with constant dissipative structure.

For an autonomous ordinary differential equations (ODEs) of the form $\frac{dy}{dt} = f(y)$, the second-order AVF method is the one-step method [20]

$$\frac{y^{n+1} - y^n}{\tau} = \int_0^1 f(\xi y^{n+1} + (1 - \xi)y^n) d\xi \tag{1.5}$$

where τ is the time step. Note that (1.5) only requires evaluations of the vector field $f(y)$. To illustrate the application of the AVF method (1.5) for the Hamiltonian system, we consider the Hamiltonian ODE

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} p \\ q \end{pmatrix} = J \begin{pmatrix} H_p(p, q) \\ H_q(p, q) \end{pmatrix}, \quad J = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad p, q \in \mathbb{R} \tag{1.6}$$

The application of the second-order AVF method (1.5) to the Hamiltonian system (1.6) gives

$$\frac{1}{\tau} \begin{pmatrix} p^{n+1} - p^n \\ q^{n+1} - q^n \end{pmatrix} = J \int_0^1 \begin{pmatrix} H_p(\xi p^{n+1} + (1 - \xi)p^n, \xi q^{n+1} + (1 - \xi)q^n) \\ H_q(\xi p^{n+1} + (1 - \xi)p^n, \xi q^{n+1} + (1 - \xi)q^n) \end{pmatrix} d\xi \tag{1.7}$$

It can be shown that the discretization (1.7) preserves the discrete Hamiltonian (energy) $H(p^n, q^n)$, that is $H(p^{n+1}, q^{n+1}) = H(p^n, q^n)$ [19]. The AVF method has been

successfully applied to many PDEs such as three-dimensional Maxwell's equations [25], St. Venant-Kirchhoff Deformable Models [26], strongly coupled nonlinear Schrödinger system [27], fractional coupled nonlinear Schrödinger equations [28], option pricing [29], bi-Hamiltonian partial differential equations [23] and two dimensional Klein-Gordon-Zakharov equations [30]. In general, the evaluation of the integral in (1.5) leads to a nonlinear function of y^{n+1} which results a fully implicit numerical scheme. In order to eliminate this disadvantage of AVF method, Cai et.al. [31] proposed the so-called Partitioned Average Vector Field (PAVF) method by dividing the variables into groups and then applies the AVF method for each variable step by step.

The application of the first-order one-step PAVF method to the Hamiltonian system (1.6) yields,

$$\frac{1}{\tau} \begin{pmatrix} p^{n+1} - p^n \\ q^{n+1} - q^n \end{pmatrix} = J \begin{pmatrix} \int_0^1 H_p(\xi p^{n+1} + (1 - \xi)p^n, q^n) d\xi \\ \int_0^1 H_q(p^{n+1}, \xi q^{n+1} + (1 - \xi)q^n) d\xi \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.8)$$

Taking the scalar product with

$$\begin{pmatrix} \int_0^1 H_p(\xi p^{n+1} + (1 - \xi)p^n, q^n) d\xi \\ \int_0^1 H_q(p^{n+1}, \xi q^{n+1} + (1 - \xi)q^n) d\xi \end{pmatrix}^T$$

on both sides of (1.8), using the Fundamental Theorem of Calculus and the skew-symmetry of J , one can obtain $H(p^{n+1}, q^{n+1}) = H(p^n, q^n)$ (see [31]). The main advantage of the PAVF method is to separate variables into different groups and apply the AVF method only for one group during each step, which lead to much simpler schemes that usually require less computational effort comparing with AVF method. Cai et. al. [31] applied the PAVF method to the Hénon-Heiles system system and the Klein-Gordon Schrödinger equations and obtained semi-implicit and explicit schemes, respectively. Aydin et.al. [32] applied the PAVF scheme to the Zakharov equation and obtained an explicit scheme, too. However, application of the PAVF method to the coupled 1-D and 2-D Schrödinger-Boussinesq equations yields semi-implicit schemes [33].

If we denote the method in (1.8) as Ψ then the corresponding adjoint method Ψ^* can be written as

$$\frac{1}{\tau} \begin{pmatrix} p^{n+1} - p^n \\ q^{n+1} - q^n \end{pmatrix} = J \begin{pmatrix} \int_0^1 H_p(\xi p^{n+1} + (1 - \xi)p^n, q^{n+1}) d\xi \\ \int_0^1 H_q(p^n, \xi q^{n+1} + (1 - \xi)q^n) d\xi \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.9)$$

The adjoint method Ψ^* (1.9) is a PAVF method with the integration path taken in reverse order relative to (1.8). Hence, it exactly preserves the Hamiltonian $H(z)$ and inherits all properties of the PAVF method.

The composite method PAVF-C is defined as a composition of the PAVF method Ψ (1.8) and its adjoint method Ψ^* (1.9)

$$\eta_\tau := \Psi_{\frac{\tau}{2}} \circ \Psi_{\frac{\tau}{2}}^* \quad (1.10)$$

Average of the PAVF method Ψ (1.8) and its adjoint method Ψ^* (1.9) gives the PAVF plus (PAVF-P) method

$$\eta_\tau := \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_\tau + \Psi_\tau^*). \quad (1.11)$$

In this paper, we consider an infinite-dimensional Hamiltonian form of the KGS equations. Applying the compact discretization to spatial direction, we convert the KGS equations into finite-dimensional ordinary differential equations (ODEs) with initial values. Then discretizing the semi-discrete ODEs based on discrete gradient AVF method and PAVF method, respectively, we obtain several new energy-preserving schemes. The paper is organized as follows: In Sec. 2 five new energy preserving compact schemes are proposed for numerical solution of the KGS equation. Numerical results with comparison of the methods and simulations of solitons are given in Sec. 3. Finally, some concluding remarks are given in Sec. 4

2 Construction of a novel conservative compact finite difference scheme

Introducing the auxiliary variables $\psi(x, t) = p(x, t) + iq(x, t)$, $\phi_t(x, t) = 2v(x, t)$, the KGS equation (1.1) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} q_t &= -\frac{1}{2}p_{xx} - p\phi \\ v_t &= \frac{1}{2}[\phi_{xx} - \phi + (p^2 + q^2)] \\ p_t &= \frac{1}{2}q_{xx} + q\phi \\ \phi_t &= 2v \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

The system (2.1) can be cast into the infinite-dimensional Hamiltonian system

$$\frac{dz}{dt} = J \frac{\delta H(z)}{\delta z}, \quad J = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad z = \begin{pmatrix} q \\ v \\ p \\ \phi \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.2)$$

where the Hamiltonian is

$$H(z) = \int_a^b -\frac{1}{2}\phi(p^2 + q^2) + \frac{1}{4} \phi^2 + \phi_x^2 + p_x^2 + q_x^2 + v^2 \, dx. \quad (2.3)$$

The numerical treatment of the KGS equation (2.2) has two sequential discretizations; spatial and temporal discretization. In this study we focus on compact finite difference scheme [16] for the space discretization of the KGS equation (1.1) and get a semi-discrete system. The time-discretization is divided into two types: (i) the AVF method (1.7) and (ii) the PAVF method (1.8).

Let J and N be two positive integers. Denote $h = (b - a)/J$, $\tau = T/N$, $\Omega_h = \{x_j = a + jh, j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, J\}$, $\Omega_\tau = \{t_n = n\tau, n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N\}$ and $\Omega_h^\tau = \Omega_h \times \Omega_\tau$. Suppose $w = \{w_j^n | j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, J, n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N\}$ is a grid function on Ω_h^τ . We introduced the following notations:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_t w_j^n &= \frac{w_j^{n+1} - w_j^n}{\tau}, & \delta_x w_j^n &= \frac{w_{j+1}^n - w_j^n}{h}, & w_j^{n+1/2} &= \frac{w_j^{n+1} + w_j^n}{2} \\ \delta_x^2 w_j^n &= \frac{w_{j+1}^n - 2w_j^n + w_{j-1}^n}{h^2}, & A_h w_j^n &= \frac{w_{j+1}^n h + 10w_j^n + w_{j-1}^n}{12}, & (w^n, v^n) &= h \sum_{j=1}^J w_j^n v_j^n \\ ||w^n|| &= h \sum_{j=1}^{J-1} |w_j^n|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

The most popular second-order finite difference scheme which approximates the second-order derivative is the three-point stencil

$$\frac{d^2 w_j}{dx^2} = \delta_x^2 w_j = \frac{w_{j+1} - 2w_j + w_{j-1}}{h^2} = O(h^2), \quad w_j \in \Omega_h.$$

To improve the order of accuracy in the approximation, we can develop the stencil with more points, such as the five points stencil

$$\frac{d^2 w_j}{dx^2} = \frac{-w_{j+2} + 16w_{j+1} - 30w_j + 16w_{j-1} - w_{j-2}}{12h^2} + O(h^4), \quad w_j^n \in \Omega_h.$$

However, there are two significant obstacles for five points stencil : (i) some additional boundary conditions are needed, (ii) at every step of the algebraic equation we must solve five-diagonal matrix instead of a three-diagonal matrix which increases the number of arithmetic operations. An alternative approach to improve the order of accuracy is to use compact finite difference scheme [16]. For instance, a fourth-order compact finite difference approximation for the second-order derivative $d^2w/dx^2 = w''$ is given as

$$\frac{w''_{j+1} + 10w''_j + w''_{j-1}}{12} = \frac{w_{j+1} - 2w_j + w_{j-1}}{h^2} \tag{2.5}$$

i.e. $\frac{d^2w_j}{dx^2} = A_h^{-1} \delta_x^2 w_j + O(h^4)$, $w_j^n \in \Omega_h$.

Applying the 4th order compact method (2.5) for discretization of spatial derivatives of the infinite dimensional Hamiltonian system (2.2), we can obtain the semi-discrete system

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dQ}{dt} + \frac{1}{2} A_h^{-1} \delta_x^2 P + \Phi \cdot P &= 0 \\ \frac{dV}{dt} - \frac{1}{2} A_h^{-1} \delta_x^2 \Phi + \frac{1}{2} \Phi - \frac{1}{2} P \cdot^2 + Q \cdot^2 &= 0 \\ \frac{dP}{dt} - \frac{1}{2} A_h^{-1} \delta_x^2 Q - \Phi \cdot Q &= 0 \\ \frac{d\Phi}{dt} - 2V &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{2.6}$$

where $P = (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_J)^T$, $Q = (q_1, q_2, \dots, q_J)^T$, $\Phi = (\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_J)^T$, $V = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_J)^T$, $\Phi \cdot Q = [\phi_1 p_1, \phi_2 p_2, \dots, \phi_J p_J]^T$, $P \cdot^2 = [p_1^2, p_2^2, \dots, p_J^2]^T$ and $Q \cdot^2 = [q_1^2, q_2^2, \dots, q_J^2]^T$. The semi-discrete system (2.6) can be cast into the finite-dimensional Hamiltonian system

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} Q \\ V \\ P \\ \Phi \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I}_J & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{I}_J \\ -\mathbf{I}_J & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I}_J & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} Q \\ V \\ P \\ \Phi \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} A_h^{-1} \delta_x^2 Q - \Phi \cdot Q \\ 2V \\ -\frac{1}{2} A_h^{-1} \delta_x^2 P - \Phi \cdot P \\ -\frac{1}{2} A_h^{-1} \delta_x^2 \Phi + \frac{1}{2} \Phi - \frac{1}{2} (P \cdot^2 + Q \cdot^2) \end{pmatrix} \tag{2.7}$$

where $\mathbf{0}$ and \mathbf{I}_J are $J \times J$ zero and identity matrices, respectively and the discrete Hamiltonian is

$$H(Q, V, P, \Phi) = \frac{1}{4} \begin{pmatrix} h & & & \\ & -P^T \tilde{D} P & -Q^T \tilde{D} Q & -\Phi^T \tilde{D} \Phi \\ & & & +4V^T V \\ & & & -2\Phi^T \cdot (P \cdot^2 + Q \cdot^2) \end{pmatrix} \tag{2.8}$$

where $\tilde{D} = A_h^{-1} \delta_x^2$. Now, we can discretize the finite-dimensional Hamiltonian system (2.7) by using the energy preserving AVF scheme (1.7) and the PAVF schemes (1.8).

2.1 Implicit Compact AVF scheme

We discretize the finite-dimensional Hamiltonian system (2.7) for the KGS equation (1.1) by using the energy preserving AVF scheme and get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \delta_t Q^n + \frac{1}{2} K P^{n+1/2} + \frac{1}{6} \Phi^{n+1} \cdot P^{n+1} + 4\Phi^{n+1/2} \cdot P^{n+1/2} + \Phi^n \cdot P^n &= 0 \\
 \delta_t V^n - \frac{1}{2} F \Phi^{n+1/2} - \frac{1}{6} (P^{n+1})^2 + 4(P^{n+1/2})^2 + (P^n)^2 & \\
 + (Q^{n+1})^2 + 4(Q^{n+1/2})^2 + (Q^n)^2 &= 0 \quad (2.9) \\
 \delta_t P^n - \frac{1}{2} K Q^{n+1/2} - \frac{1}{6} \Phi^{n+1} \cdot Q^{n+1} + 4\Phi^{n+1/2} \cdot Q^{n+1/2} + \Phi^n \cdot Q^n &= 0 \\
 \delta_t \Phi^n - V^n - V^{n+1} &= 0.
 \end{aligned}$$

It is clear from (1.7) that the compact AVF method (2.9) preserves the energy (2.8) exactly, i.e.,

$$H(Q^{n+1}, V^{n+1}, P^{n+1}, \Phi^{n+1}) = H(Q^n, V^n, P^n, \Phi^n), \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N.$$

Remark: Note that the scheme (2.9) is a fully implicit scheme which can be solve by an iterative method such as a fixed-point iteration or the Newton-Raphson’s method. Here , Newton-Raphson’s method is used to solve Q^1, V^1, P^1, Φ^1 using initial condition Q^0, V^0, P^0, Φ^0).

2.2 Linearly implicit compact PAVF scheme

Next, applying the PAVF method (1.8) to the finite-dimensional Hamiltonian system (2.7), we obtain the compact PAVF scheme for the KGS equation (1.1)

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{1}{\tau} (Q^{n+1} - Q^n) + \frac{1}{4} K (P^{n+1} + P^n) + \frac{1}{2} \Phi_{n+1} \cdot (P_{n+1} + P_n) &= 0 \\
 \frac{1}{\tau} (V^{n+1} - V^n) - \frac{1}{4} F (\Phi^{n+1} + \Phi^n) - \frac{1}{2} (P^n)^2 + (Q^n) &= 0 \\
 \frac{1}{\tau} (P^{n+1} - P^n) - \frac{1}{4} K (Q^{n+1} + Q^n) - \frac{1}{2} \Phi^{n+1} \cdot (Q^{n+1} + Q^n) &= 0 \quad (2.10) \\
 \frac{1}{\tau} (\Phi^{n+1} - \Phi^n) - V^{n+1} - V^n &= 0
 \end{aligned}$$

where $K = A_h^{-1} \delta_x^2$ and $F = K - I_j$. It is clear from (1.8) that the compact PAVF method (2.10) preserves the energy (2.8) exactly, i.e.,

$$H(Q^{n+1}, P^{n+1}) = H(Q^n, P^n), \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N.$$

Moreover, the compact PAVF method (2.10) also conserves the mass $M(t)$ of the system (2.7) in discrete level as stated in the following theorem.

Theorem 1 *The PAVF method (2.10) conserves the mass of the system (2.7) in the discrete level, i.e.*

$$M(Q^{n+1}, P^{n+1}) = M(Q^n, P^n), \quad \forall n = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (2.11)$$

where

$$M(Q^n, P^n) = \|Q^n\|^2 + \|P^n\|^2 \quad (2.12)$$

Proof: Taking the discrete inner products of first equation in (2.10) with $Q^{n+1} + Q^n$ and taking the discrete inner products of third equation in (2.10) with $P^{n+1} + P^n$ and respectively, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\tau}(Q^{n+1} - Q^n) \cdot (Q^{n+1} + Q^n) + \frac{1}{4}K(P^{n+1} + P^n) \cdot (Q^{n+1} + Q^n) \\ + \frac{1}{2}\Phi^{n+1} \cdot (P^{n+1} + P^n) \cdot (Q^{n+1} + Q^n) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\tau}(P^{n+1} - P^n) \cdot (P^{n+1} + P^n) - \frac{1}{4}K(Q^{n+1} + Q^n) \cdot (P^{n+1} + P^n) \\ - \frac{1}{2}\Phi^{n+1} \cdot (Q^{n+1} + Q^n) \cdot (P^{n+1} + P^n) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Summing these equations together, we get

$$\frac{1}{\tau} (\|P^{n+1}\|^2 + \|Q^{n+1}\|^2 - \|P^n\|^2 - \|Q^n\|^2) = 0$$

which proves the conservation of discrete mass.

The conservation of the discrete mass (2.11) implies that the scheme PAVF scheme (2.10) is unconditionally stable for computing the component $\psi(x, t) = p(x, t) + iq(x, t)$ in the KGS equation (1.1).

Remark: Contrary to the AVF scheme (2.9), the PAVF scheme (2.10) is a linearly implicit scheme which is suitable for parallel computing. When P^n, Q^n, V^n , and Φ^n are known, the variables V^{n+1} and Φ^{n+1} can be obtained from the second and fourth equations in (2.10). Then V^{n+1} and Φ^{n+1} are substituted into the first and the third equations and P^{n+1} and Q^{n+1} are computed.

2.3 Linearly implicit compact PAVF Adjoint scheme

Next we introduce the adjoint scheme (1.9) associated to the PAVF scheme (2.10) for the semi-discrete KGS equation (2.7)

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{1}{\tau}(Q^{n+1} - Q^n) + \frac{1}{4}K(P^{n+1} + P^n) + \frac{1}{2}\Phi_n \cdot (P_{n+1} + P_n) &= 0 \\
 \frac{1}{\tau}(V^{n+1} - V^n) - \frac{1}{4}F(\Phi^{n+1} + \Phi^n) - \frac{1}{2}(P^{n+1})^2 + (Q^{n+1}) &= 0 \\
 \frac{1}{\tau}(P^{n+1} - P^n) - \frac{1}{4}K(Q^{n+1} + Q^n) - \frac{1}{2}\Phi^n \cdot (Q^{n+1} + Q^n) &= 0 \\
 \frac{1}{\tau}(\Phi^{n+1} - \Phi^n) - V^{n+1} - V^n &= 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.13}$$

Note that the scheme (2.13) is linearly implicit as (2.10). Since P^n , Q^n , V^n , and Φ^n are known, the variables P^{n+1} and Q^{n+1} can be obtained from the first and third equations in (2.13). P^{n+1} and Q^{n+1} are substituted into the second and the fourth equations in (2.13), and then, V^{n+1} and Φ^{n+1} are computed from the second and fourth equations. Following the Theorem 1, it can shown that the adjoint scheme (2.13) also conserves the discrete mass (2.11).

2.4 Linearly implicit compact PAVF-C scheme

The second-order energy-preserving PAVF composition (PAVF-C) method is constructed by composing the PAVF method (2.10) with its adjoint method (2.13). The PAVF-C method for the KGS equation (1.1) can be given as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{2}{\tau}(Q^* - Q^n) + \frac{1}{4}K(P^* + P^n) + \frac{1}{2}\Phi^* \cdot (P^* + P^n) &= 0 \\
 \frac{2}{\tau}(V^* - V^n) - \frac{1}{4}F(\Phi^* + \Phi^n) - \frac{1}{2}(P^n)^2 + (Q^n)^2 &= 0 \\
 \frac{2}{\tau}(P^* - P^n) - \frac{1}{4}K(Q^* + Q^n) - \frac{1}{2}\Phi^* \cdot (Q^* + Q^n) &= 0 \\
 \frac{2}{\tau}(\Phi^* - \Phi^n) - V^* - V^n &= 0 \\
 \frac{2}{\tau}(Q^{n+1} - Q^*) + \frac{1}{4}K(P^{n+1} + P^*) + \frac{1}{2}\Phi^* \cdot (P^{n+1} + P^*) &= 0 \\
 \frac{2}{\tau}(V^{n+1} - V^*) - \frac{1}{4}F(\Phi^{n+1} + \Phi^*) - \frac{1}{2}(P^*)^2 + (Q^*)^2 &= 0 \\
 \frac{2}{\tau}(P^{n+1} - P^*) - \frac{1}{4}K(Q^{n+1} + Q^*) - \frac{1}{2}\Phi^* \cdot (Q^{n+1} + Q^*) &= 0 \\
 \frac{2}{\tau}(\Phi^{n+1} - \Phi^*) - V^{n+1} - V^* &= 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.14}$$

Being the composition of two linearly implicit schemes, method (2.14) is linearly implicit as well. Moreover, since this scheme is the composition of energy and mass conserving schemes, it also conserves the discrete energy (2.8) and discrete mass (2.11).

2.5 Implicit compact PAVF-P scheme

Finally, the second-order energy-preserving PAVF plus (PAVF-P) method for the KGS equation (1.1) can be constructed as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{1}{\tau}(Q^{n+1} - Q^n) + \frac{1}{4}K(P^{n+1} + P^n) + \frac{1}{4}(\Phi^{n+1} + \Phi^n) \cdot (P^{n+1} + P^n) &= 0 \\
 \frac{1}{\tau}(V^{n+1} - V^n) - \frac{1}{4}F(\Phi^{n+1} + \Phi^n) - \frac{1}{4}(P^n)^2 + (Q^n) &= 0 \\
 &\quad - \frac{1}{4}(P^{n+1})^2 + (Q^{n+1}) &= 0 \quad (2.15) \\
 \frac{1}{\tau}(P^{n+1} - P^n) - \frac{1}{4}K(Q^{n+1} + Q^n) - \frac{1}{4}(\Phi^{n+1} + \Phi^n) \cdot (Q^{n+1} + Q^n) &= 0 \\
 \frac{1}{\tau}(\Phi^{n+1} - \Phi^n) - V^{n+1} - V^n &= 0
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that, the system (2.15) is not linearly implicit but it is nonlinear in P^{n+1} , Q^{n+1} , V^{n+1} and Φ^{n+1} which can be solve by an iterative method. Here, we use the Newton method for solving P^{n+1} , Q^{n+1} , V^{n+1} and Φ^{n+1} . Moreover, since this scheme is sum of energy and mass conserving schemes, it also conserves the discrete energy (2.8) and discrete mass (2.11).

3 Numerical Experiment

In this section, we present several numerical results obtained by applying five energy-preserving compact methods, i.e. AVF (2.9), PAVF (2.10), PAVF-ADJ (2.13), PAVF-C (2.14) and PAVF-P (2.15). To assess their conservation properties, the relative energy and mass errors at $t = t_n$ are defined as follows:

$$RH^n = |(H^n - H^0)/H^0|, \quad RM^n = |(M^n - M^0)/M^0| \quad (3.1)$$

where $H^n = H(Q^n, V^n, P^n, \Phi^n)$ and $M^n = H(Q^n, P^n)$ are defined in (2.8) and (2.12), respectively. The error for the numerical solutions of the KGS equation is computed by the discrete L^∞ - error

$$e_\infty(\psi(t_n)) = \|\psi(t_n) - \psi^n\|_\infty, \quad e_\infty(\phi(t_n)) = \|\phi(t_n) - \phi^n\|_\infty. \quad (3.2)$$

The KG equation (1.1) admits soliton solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 \psi(x, t) &= \frac{\sqrt{3-2}}{4(1-c^2)} \operatorname{sech}^2 \frac{\sqrt{1}}{2(1-c^2)}(x - ct - x_0) \exp i(cx + \frac{1-c^2+c^4}{2(1-c^2)}t) , \\
 \phi(x, t) &= \frac{3}{4(1-c^2)} \operatorname{sech}^2 \frac{\sqrt{1}}{2(1-c^2)}(x - ct - x_0)
 \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

where $|c| < 1$ is the propagation speed of the wave, and x_0 represents the initial phase. In all numerical simulation of the wave profiles, the results obtained by the compact PAVF scheme (2.10) will be represented since the wave profiles obtained by the other schemes are similar.

3.1 Single Soliton

To test the performance of the proposed methods, first we examine the propagation of a single soliton. The initial conditions

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(x, 0) &= \frac{\sqrt[3]{2}}{4\sqrt{1-c^2}} \operatorname{sech}^2 \frac{x-x_0}{2\sqrt{1-c^2}} \exp(icx), \\ \phi(x, 0) &= \frac{3}{4(1-c^2)} \operatorname{sech}^2 \frac{x-x_0}{2\sqrt{1-c^2}}, \\ \phi_t(x, 0) &= \frac{3v}{4(1-c^2)^{3/2}} \operatorname{sech}^2 \frac{x-x_0}{2\sqrt{1-c^2}} \tanh \frac{x-x_0}{2\sqrt{1-c^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

are taken from the exact solution (3.3) with $c = -0.8$ at $t = 0$.

First, we test the accuracy of the schemes. We consider the equation (1.1) with the initial conditions (3.4). We solve the problem on the interval $-50 \leq x \leq 50$ with $h = 0.125$ until $T = 1$. The results are shown in Table 1. From the table we we can see that all the methods are second-order accurate in time except the PAVF method which is only first order. Next, we test the stability of the proposed methods by using mesh size h and time step τ at different rate $r = \tau/h$. Since the discrete mass conservation implies that PAVF, PAVF-ADJ, PAVF-C and PAVF-P methods are unconditionally stable in computing the component $\psi(x, t)$ in KGS equation, we focus on the stability test for computing the other component $\phi(x, t)$ in KGS equation. Tables 2 and 3 shows the errors $e_\infty(\phi)$ and $e_\infty(\psi)$, respectively. The tables report that no numerical instabilities have been observed for different rates $r = \tau/h$.

Now, we can simulate the dynamics of the solitons (3.3). Figure 1 shows the evolution of single wave initially located at the position $x_0 = 0$ on the interval $-32 \leq x \leq 32$ for $0 \leq t \leq 40$. It can be seen that the compact PAVF scheme (2.10) can simulate the single soliton very well for a long time.

To validate the numerical methods further more, we test the conserved quantities, the energy (2.8) and the mass (2.12). Figure 2 shows both relative energy error RH^n and relative mass error RM^n in (3.1). We see that conserved quantities (2.8) and (2.12) are conserved by all schemes. Furthermore, all compact PAVF methods appear to be superior to the compact AVF method in terms of mass conservation.

	τ	$e_\infty(\phi)$	order	$e_\infty(\psi)$	order
AVF	1/10	3.531310e-03	—	5.774787e-03	—
	1/11	2.931657e-03	1.9526	4.775481e-03	1.9936
	1/12	2.473494e-03	1.9530	4.013723e-03	1.9972
	1/13	2.115706e-03	1.9520	3.419997e-03	1.9999
PAVF	1/10	3.211935e-02	—	7.599502e-02	—
	1/11	2.901042e-02	1.0213	6.949625e-02	0.8878
	1/12	2.644590e-02	1.0157	6.401309e-02	0.8905
	1/13	2.429518e-02	1.0132	5.932615e-02	0.8933
PAVF-C	1/10	8.210417e-04	—	8.430187e-04	—
	1/11	6.851074e-04	1.8906	6.760921e-04	2.1478
	1/12	5.817526e-04	1.8912	5.524118e-04	2.1526
	1/13	5.013390e-04	1.8898	4.589771e-04	2.1462
PAVF-P	1/10	1.935742e-03	—	4.084042e-03	—
	1/11	1.609453e-03	1.8912	3.376916e-03	1.9011
	1/12	1.360462e-03	1.8905	2.837704e-03	1.9002
	1/13	1.166192e-03	1.8898	2.417390e-03	1.8994

Table 1: Comparison of the temporal accuracy of four energy-preserving methods for single soliton with different time step sizes with $h = 0.125$, $T = 1$.

Figure 1: Profiles of a single soliton obtained by the compact PAVF scheme (2.10) for $\tau = 0.01$, $h = 0.2$.

Figure 2: Relative energy error and relative mass error of four energy-preserving methods for the evolution of a single soliton. $\tau = 0.01$, $h = 0.2$.

$h = 0.2$	$\tau = h$	$\tau = h/2$	$\tau = h/4$
AVF	3.574313e-02	9.858316e-03	3.126925e-03
PAVF	7.230295e-02	2.461892e-02	9.577223e-03
PAVF-C	5.475593e-03	2.041844e-03	1.971309e-03
PAVF-P	2.245555e-02	6.39937e-03	2.291053e-03
$h = 0.1$	$\tau = h$	$\tau = h/2$	$\tau = h/4$
AVF	8.945973e-03	2.302452e-03	6.158300e-04
PAVF	2.379871e-02	8.756432e-03	3.623246e-03
PAVF-C	1.201833e-03	3.418482e-04	1.273630e-04
PAVF-P	5.677344e-03	1.464343e-03	4.088853e-04

Table 2: Stability test for ϕ at $T = 3$ with mesh size h and time step τ at different rate $r = \tau/h$

$h = 0.2$	$\tau = h$	$\tau = h/2$	$\tau = h/4$
AVF	2.221000e-02	5.881537e-03	2.297252e-03
$h = 0.1$	$\tau = h$	$\tau = h/2$	$\tau = h/4$
AVF	5.255411e-03	1.311413e-03	3.574160e-04

Table 3: Stability test for ψ at $T = 3$ with mesh size h and time step τ at different rate $r = \tau/h$.

	AVF	PAVF	PAVF-P	PAVF-C
T=2	35.9648	2.6311	19.2738	3.6248
T=4	61.0073	3.9045	35.9958	7.3234
T=6	98.3374	5.2441	54.1268	11.7569
T=8	121.697552	6.7319	71.9398	16.0587
T=10	163.915267	15.014625	89.2549	19.7762

Table 4: CPU times with time step sizes $\tau = 0.1$.

We record the CPU time of the schemes with different time in Table 4. Since the PAVF and PAVF-C methods are linearly implicit methods, comparing the computational cost of the PAVF method with that of the PAVF-C method would be fair. On the other hand, since the PAVF-P and AVF methods are fully implicit methods, comparing their computational costs among themselves would be a fairer comparison. From the table we see that the CPU times of the nonlinear schemes are more than the that of linearly implicit schemes as expected. Moreover, although the PAVF-C scheme calls both PAVF and its adjoint scheme at every time step, the CPU time of the PAVF-C method is much less than the twice of that of the PAVF method which coincides with [31].

3.2 Collision of two solitons

Next, we investigate the dynamics of two colliding solitons, using the initial conditions

$$\begin{aligned}
 \psi(x, 0) &= \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{4\sqrt{1-c_i^2}} \operatorname{sech}^2 \frac{\sqrt{1-c_i^2}}{2} (x-x_i) \exp(ic_i x), \\
 \phi(x, 0) &= \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{3}{4(1-c_i^2)} \operatorname{sech}^2 \frac{\sqrt{1-c_i^2}}{2} (x-x_i), \\
 \phi_t(x, 0) &= \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{3c_i}{4(1-c_i^2)^{3/2}} \operatorname{sech}^2 \frac{\sqrt{1-c_i^2}}{2} (x-x_i) \tanh \frac{\sqrt{1-c_i^2}}{2} (x-x_i)
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

The interactions of two solitons over the time interval $[0, 40]$ are depicted in Fig. 3. From the figure, it can be seen that the solitary waves propagate in their original direction with changing the amplitude and the interaction is inelastic. The corresponding energy and mass conservation are shown in Fig. 4. From the figure, we can see that there is a rapid increase in the error of energy conservation of the compact AVF method and the compact PAVF-P method at $t \approx 25$ where the interaction takes place. Moreover, we can see that the exact preservation of mass by the compact PAVF methods which verifies the Theorem 1. On the other hand, the error in the mass conservation reveals that the compact AVF method is not mass conserving. These results are consistent with the results in [31].

Figure 3: Profiles of a two solitons obtained using four energy-preserving methods for $\tau = 0.01, h = 0.2$.

Figure 4: Relative energy error and relative mass error of four energy-preserving methods for the evolution of two solitons. $\tau = 0.01, h = 0.2$.

	AVF	PAVF	PAVF-P	PAVF-C
T=2	35.9422	2.4491	18.2326	4.0851
T=4	72.5606	4.0973	34.6110	7.6351
T=6	105.0767	6.1507	51.9199	11.3036
T=8	135.2441	8.9579	71.6805	14.6767
T=10	166.637534	11.0029	88.8790	20.3929

Table 5: CPU times with time step sizes $\tau = 0.1$ for collision of two solitons.

The Table 5 represents the CPU times of the compact methods in collision scenario. We can see that the CPU times in collision scenario of the methods are almost same with the CPU time of the methods in single solitary wave evolution as given in the Table 4).

4 Conclusion

In the present paper, some new structure preserving finite difference method have been proposed for the solution of the KGS equation. The KGS equation is discretized in space by using a fourth-order compact scheme and finite dimensional Hamiltonian system is obtained. Then the semi-discrete system is discretized by the energy preserving AVF method and the energy preserving PAVF method in time. In conjunction with the PAVF method PAVF composition method and the PAVF plus method are also introduced for the solution of the KGS equation. It has been proven that the PAVF method not only conserves the energy of the compact scheme but also conserves that discrete mass which implies the unconditional stability. Numerical experiments are carried out to verify the theoretical analysis.

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